

Mapping Urban Food Sharing at Scale: Discovering and Classifying Food Sharing Initiatives Across 105 European Cities

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Abstract

Urban food sharing initiatives—including community fridges, food banks, gleaning networks, cooperative kitchens, and surplus redistribution platforms—represent a growing segment of the urban sustainability landscape. Despite increasing scholarly and policy interest, there is currently no widely adopted and systematically documented methodology for mapping such initiatives at continental scale. This paper presents a methodology developed in the EU Horizon Europe project CULTIVATE (Grant Agreement No. 101083377), including an end-to-end data pipeline for discovering, classifying, and curating food sharing initiatives (FSIs) across 105 European cities. The pipeline integrates multilingual web discovery across 25 languages, large language model (LLM)-assisted classification using an agent-based, on-the-fly retrieval approach, structured human-in-the-loop verification, and a medallion data architecture for progressive data refinement and quality assurance.

Across five iterative rounds, the system processed approximately 210,000 candidate URLs per iteration (around 3 GB of extracted unstructured text), improving classification accuracy on a fixed reference set from 32% to 74% through prompt refinement, exclusion rule development, and architectural changes. The resulting dataset comprises approximately 3,000 validated FSIs after multi-strategy deduplication and forms the empirical basis of the Food Sharing Map hosted on the Sharing Solutions platform. We document the full pipeline methodology, report accuracy trajectories and deduplication outcomes, and discuss the challenges of multilingual web-based discovery and the role of human oversight in LLM-assisted classification. The pipeline and its design principles provide a reusable methodological framework for large-scale, web-based discovery and curation of community-level initiatives in other policy-relevant domains.

Keywords

food sharing, urban sustainability, data pipeline, LLM classification, web discovery, data curation, Horizon Europe

1 Introduction

Food sharing—including community gardens, community kitchens, food banks, gleaning networks, and surplus redistribution initiatives—has become an increasingly visible element of urban sustainability practice across Europe (Davies et al. 2017; Morrow 2019). These initiatives operate in cities of different sizes and socio-economic contexts, frequently addressing food waste, food insecurity, and social connection at the same time. As a result, food sharing has attracted growing attention within urban studies, sustainability research, and food policy debates.

Yet, despite this expanding interest, there is still no comprehensive and up-to-date inventory of food sharing initiatives at a continental scale. Existing mapping efforts tend to focus on selected cities or national contexts and are often produced through manual identification processes that are difficult to reproduce, compare, or maintain over time. Consequently, cross-city analysis remains limited, and empirical understanding of the spatial distribution and diversity of food sharing practices remains fragmented.

In response to this situation, the EU Horizon Europe project CULTIVATE (Grant Agreement No. 101083377) set out to develop new ways of documenting food sharing activity at scale. Within CULTIVATE, Work Package 2 (WP2), led by Trinity College Dublin, established the **Food Sharing Map**—a public, interactive resource hosted on the Sharing Solutions platform¹—covering initiatives across 105 European cities. The scope of this work, spanning 25 languages and a wide variety of online representations, required an approach capable of operating across heterogeneous sources while remaining adaptable and transparent.

This paper describes the methodology developed to meet that challenge. It introduces a data pipeline that combines multilingual

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¹<https://www.sharingsolutions.eu/>

web discovery, LLM-assisted classification, and structured manual verification within a process of progressive refinement. Rather than treating mapping as a one-off data collection exercise, the pipeline was designed to be repeatable, with insights from verification feeding directly into subsequent iterations of the classification logic.

Designing such a system raises several practical and analytical difficulties. In this study, these challenges appeared in at least five recurring forms:

- **Scale:** Extending coverage to 105 cities meant working with roughly 2,000 candidates per city, or around 210,000 URLs overall. Even when previously assessed links could be excluded in later runs, the initial discovery stages required substantial processing capacity.
- **Linguistic diversity:** Food sharing terminology varies across languages, and many initiatives maintain a web presence only in local or highly context-specific forms.
- **Structural heterogeneity:** Initiatives appear across websites, social media, and directory listings, rarely following consistent structural patterns.
- **Classification ambiguity:** Distinguishing operational initiatives from media coverage, commercial services, crowdfunding campaigns, or policy descriptions often depends on contextual judgement.
- **Data quality expectations:** Because the outputs support public visualisation and comparative research, records must be verifiable, deduplicated, geographically accurate, and accompanied by clear provenance.

Under these conditions, approaches based solely on manual identification encounter practical limits. Yet fully automated discovery also struggles when confronted with noisy, ambiguous, and unevenly structured representations of community activity. The methodological task, therefore, is not to remove human judgement, but to organise how automation and verification can work together in a systematic and repeatable way.

Against this background, the paper makes several contributions. It provides a methodological account of how large-scale, multilingual, and heterogeneous forms of community activity can be identified and curated through a structured combination of automated discovery and human evaluation. The framework integrates multilingual query design, geolocation procedures, and reproducible decision rules, enabling comparison across diverse contexts.

The study further shows how iterative refinement can substantially improve automated classification. Successive prompt development and systematic analysis of false positives increased accuracy on a fixed reference set from 32% to 68.8%. A subsequent transition to an agent-based classification model, in which retrieval and evaluation occur together, raised performance to 74.5% while simplifying infrastructure demands and enabling faster feedback cycles between automation and verification.

Beyond technical performance, the pipeline establishes a staged approach to data consolidation suited to research environments, where transparency, traceability, and the ability to revisit earlier decisions are essential. The project ultimately delivers a validated dataset of 3,052 food sharing initiatives across 105 cities, now available through a public interactive map, while also offering design

principles that may inform other efforts to map community-based activity through web data under conditions of ambiguity and uneven representation.

The paper now turns to the foundations that inform this approach. Section 2 situates the work within existing debates on food sharing, web-based discovery, and LLM-assisted classification. Section 3 outlines the overall pipeline design. The following sections move through implementation, from input preparation and discovery to classification, verification, and data consolidation. Section 9 presents the empirical results, followed by a discussion of methodological implications and limitations, before concluding with directions for future research.

2 Methodological foundations

This section briefly outlines the strands of work that inform the design of the pipeline. Rather than offering a comprehensive review, the aim is to situate the approach within existing efforts to document community-based activity, automate web discovery, and organise data refinement in ways that remain transparent for research use.

2.1 Mapping community-based food initiatives

Food sharing describes a wide range of practices through which food is redistributed, collectively produced, or communally consumed outside conventional market exchange (Davies et al. 2017). Previous mapping efforts, including the ShareCity project, demonstrated the value of making such activity visible across urban contexts, but relied heavily on manual identification and verification. Expanding coverage beyond selected cities raises questions of how discovery, comparison, and updating can be organised more systematically while remaining sensitive to local variation.

2.2 Automated discovery and LLM-assisted classification

The use of search APIs and automated retrieval has long been explored as a way to generate candidate organisations from the open web. However, variation in digital presence, language, and institutional form frequently produces high levels of noise. Recent advances in large language models have made it possible to interpret heterogeneous text sources with far greater flexibility, enabling classification without extensive labelled training data.

At the same time, applying LLMs in research contexts introduces new concerns around consistency, transparency, and validation. The challenge is therefore not simply to automate, but to design workflows in which model outputs can be checked, revised, and incorporated into cumulative improvement.

2.3 Staged data refinement in research settings

Research applications require data infrastructures that allow earlier decisions to be revisited and compared across iterations. The pipeline described in this paper follows a staged refinement logic, comparable to approaches widely used in data engineering practice (Databricks, 2022). Candidate URLs and extracted texts are retained as raw material, while movement into the final dataset depends on manual verification, explicit coding of false positives, and traceable

deduplication. This structure enables systematic testing of alternative prompts, models, and rules without losing the provenance of earlier classifications.

3 Pipeline organisation and refinement logic

This section explains how the pipeline was organised to support large-scale discovery while maintaining transparency, comparability, and the possibility of revision. The emphasis is less on technical infrastructure than on how methodological control was achieved across repeated runs.

3.1 Design considerations

The system was designed under four explicit constraints: multilingual discovery across 105 cities, cumulative execution across rounds, traceable linkage from each validated FSI to its source URL and review history, and separation of raw candidate material from publication-ready records.

In addition, the distinction between tentative discovery and validated knowledge had to remain explicit. Candidate URLs, intermediate assessments, and confirmed initiatives therefore required different forms of handling. Finally, because the outputs feed into public-facing resources, safeguards were necessary to prevent raw scraped material or sensitive information from appearing in dissemination products.

3.2 Overall workflow

The pipeline executes six stages: (1) multilingual query generation from city and vocabulary tables, (2) Google API retrieval of ranked candidate URLs, (3) blacklist and novelty filtering, (4) LLM-based URL classification, (5) structured manual review with false-positive coding, and (6) consolidation into candidate, assessed, and validated data layers.

Rather than moving directly from discovery to publication, the process retained materials at different levels of certainty. Raw candidates and extracted texts were preserved, intermediate decisions remained accessible for reassessment, and only verified initiatives progressed to the final dataset. This arrangement made it possible to revisit earlier judgements as classification logic evolved.

The system was designed for repeated execution rather than one-off data collection. Each round focused on newly discovered material, while prior decisions were retained, allowing cumulative learning to shape subsequent runs.

3.3 Iterative improvement across versions

The pipeline developed through successive rounds of testing and adjustment. Improvements were driven primarily by patterns identified during manual verification, which informed both prompt design and exclusion logic.

The substantial increase between early and later versions reflects cumulative methodological adjustments rather than a single intervention. Successive refinements clarified borderline cases, expanded exclusion categories, and incorporated domain knowledge gained from reviewing misclassifications.

Figure 1: Workflow and refinement cycle

3.4 Prompt refinement and exclusion logic

Changes to classification practice emerged gradually. Early updates concentrated on excluding media coverage and reporting platforms. Later iterations addressed institutional websites, umbrella organisations, and other entities that appeared frequently in search results but did not directly operate initiatives. Importantly, these modifications were introduced incrementally, enabling their effects to be observed and compared across rounds.

A detailed account of version-level adjustments is provided in Appendix E.

4 Input preparation: multilingual query design

4.1 CULTIVATE urban and peri-urban areas

The pipeline operates across 105 cities defined as urban and peri-urban areas within the CULTIVATE project. These cities span multiple European regions as well as a smaller set of neighbouring locations, creating a geographically diverse testbed for large-scale discovery. The distribution ensures variation in language, governance traditions, and digital presence, all of which shape how food sharing activity becomes visible online.

For clarity, the complete list of cities and their regional groupings is provided in Appendix A.

Table 1: Pipeline version history with classification accuracy progression. Accuracy is measured on a fixed reference set of 228 candidate URLs, including 73 confirmed FSIs.

Version	Architecture	Accuracy	Key change
v1.0.0	Crawl-and-store	32.02%	Initial baseline
v2.0.0	Crawl-and-store	68.87%	Prompt refinement through iterative human validation
v3.0.0	Agent-based	74.50%	Transition to retrieval-integrated classification

4.2 Building a multilingual vocabulary

A central challenge in discovery lies in the linguistic variability of food sharing terminology. To address this, a working vocabulary was assembled across 25 languages. The aim was not merely translation, but adaptation to local usage, recognising that equivalent practices may be described differently depending on institutional and cultural context.

Cities associated with more than one widely used language were queried accordingly. This approach increased the diversity of potential entry points and reduced the risk of systematically overlooking initiatives operating outside English-language visibility.

4.3 Constructing search queries

Query templates combined a city identifier with food-sharing vocabulary terms and optional geographic modifiers. Multiple query families were executed per city to widen recall and to reduce dependence on any single lexical formulation.

This layered approach acknowledged that community initiatives rarely describe themselves in standardised ways. By allowing different routes into the same urban context, the system prioritised recall during early stages of discovery, with precision addressed later through classification and review.

Across the full set of cities, each round produced on the order of two thousand candidate URLs per location, amounting to approximately 210,000 potential entries.

4.4 Geographic disambiguation

Ambiguity in place names required explicit methodological controls. Many cities included in the study share names with locations in other countries, and search engine results routinely returned references to these unintended places.

To mitigate this problem, multiple strategies were combined. Queries were formulated with country identifiers where possible, country or region filters provided by the search API were applied, and results were cross-checked against expected geographic information. Different filter combinations were tested in order to understand their effects on precision.

The experiments showed that stricter geographic constraints could substantially reduce cross-border noise. However, they also revealed a trade-off: highly restrictive settings sometimes excluded relevant initiatives hosted on international platforms or domains. No single configuration achieved both high precision and full recall.

Geographic attribution at the discovery stage was therefore treated as provisional. Remaining ambiguities were resolved through manual verification in later stages of the pipeline.

5 Discovery and Extraction

5.1 Google API-based URL discovery

Candidate discovery is performed through the Google Custom Search API using multilingual query templates. For each city, the API returns ranked URLs across paginated result sets, producing on the order of several thousand candidate links per city and roughly two hundred thousand URLs per full multi-city iteration.

The resulting pool is heterogeneous. It includes organisational websites, social media presences, directory listings, media articles, institutional pages, and commercial services. This diversity is expected: discovery is intentionally broad at this stage, with subsequent phases responsible for determining which results correspond to operational food sharing initiatives.

5.2 Candidate generation at scale

Across the full set of 105 cities, a single iteration produces roughly two hundred thousand candidate URLs. Repeated execution across multiple rounds generates a large and continually evolving body of material.

To prevent unnecessary repetition, URLs that have already been assessed in earlier rounds are excluded from reprocessing. This incremental logic reduces reviewer workload and ensures that effort is directed toward newly discovered material rather than revisiting earlier decisions.

Basic domain filtering is also applied prior to classification. Known sources of persistent noise, such as advertising platforms or generic search aggregators, are removed in order to stabilise downstream evaluation.

5.3 Architectural evolution

The infrastructure used to obtain and interpret web evidence changed over the course of the project.

Crawl-and-store architecture (v1.x–v2.x). Earlier versions separated retrieval from judgement. Pages were first scraped and stored, producing an intermediate text collection. The classification model then operated on this stored corpus. While this supported reproducibility and auditing, it required maintaining large amounts of material and additional processing steps between extraction and evaluation.

Agent-based architecture (v3.x). Later iterations adopted an integrated approach in which retrieval and classification occurred together. Instead of relying on previously saved content, the model accessed information dynamically at the moment of decision. This reduced storage requirements, simplified workflow management, and allowed assessments to reflect the most current version of a webpage.

Table 2: Architectural shift in how web evidence is accessed.

	Crawl-and-store	Agent-based
Retrieval	Before classification	During classification
Storage	Intermediate corpus kept	No persistent storage
Pipeline	Sequential steps	Integrated process
Freshness	Snapshot in time	Current page state

The architectural transition concerns how evidence is accessed. Changes to the criteria used to decide whether a candidate constitutes a food sharing initiative are discussed in the next section.

6 LLM-Based Classification

6.1 Agent-based on-the-fly classification

Classification is implemented through an agent-based configuration in which evidence retrieval and evaluation are combined within a single operation. Rather than maintaining a persistent corpus of scraped text, the model accesses relevant material directly from the source at the moment of assessment.

The system performs two linked functions:

1. **Content retrieval:** locating and extracting relevant information from the target page.
2. **Interpretation:** evaluating whether the material corresponds to an operational food sharing initiative in the specified city.

For each candidate URL, the process produces several structured outputs:

- a **binary decision** (`valid_fsi` or `invalid_fsi`);
- a **confidence estimate**;
- where appropriate, **categorical descriptors** such as activity type (e.g., distribution, growing, cooking & eating) and sharing mode;
- for rejected cases, a short **reason for exclusion**.

This configuration simplifies infrastructure while allowing criteria to be revised between iterations without reprocessing stored material.

6.2 Prompt design and iterative refinement

The prompts operationalise the project’s working definition of food sharing by translating it into explicit decision rules. Detailed specifications are provided in the appendices; here we highlight the core principles that guided their evolution.

To be accepted, an initiative had to demonstrate direct involvement in food redistribution, production, or collective access. References to food, sustainability, or community benefit in general terms were not sufficient. Reviewers required evidence of organisational responsibility, continuity of activity, and a clear relationship to the target city.

Much of the retrieved material, however, concerned food sharing only indirectly. Exclusion rules therefore became central to improving precision. These rules addressed recurrent patterns observed during verification, including:

- media coverage describing initiatives rather than representing them (`FP_MEDIA`);

- commercial services such as restaurants or delivery platforms (`FP_COMMERCIAL`);
- fundraising or crowdfunding pages (`FP_CROWDFUNDING`);
- exhibitions or cultural programming (`FP_MUSEUM`);
- policy descriptions without operational activity (`FP_GOVERNMENT`);
- organisations that support or fund food sharing without directly operating initiatives (`FP_SUPPORTING_ORG`).

These criteria accumulated gradually. Ambiguous cases identified through manual review were categorised, compared, and converted into clearer instructions for subsequent runs. Prompt design thus became a mechanism for stabilising situated judgement into reproducible computational guidance.

6.3 Accuracy improvement trajectory

Performance was monitored using a fixed reference set of 228 candidate URLs, of which 73 were confirmed initiatives. Across iterations, accuracy improved as recurring ambiguities were formalised into clearer rules.

- **v1.0.0 (baseline):** 32.02% accuracy, with a large number of false positives.
- **v2.0.0 (refined prompts):** 68.87%, reflecting further consolidation of exclusion logic.
- **v3.0.0 (agent-based):** 74.50%, after integrating retrieval and evaluation within the same operation.

The overall improvement cannot be attributed to model change alone. Rather, it reflects cumulative learning generated through repeated cycles of review, categorisation, and redesign.

7 Manual Verification and Quality Assurance

Automated classification enabled coverage at continental scale, but inclusion in the published dataset required explicit human confirmation. Manual verification therefore acted as the stabilising component of the pipeline, ensuring that mapped entities corresponded to real and operational initiatives.

7.1 Verification procedure

For each city and iteration, reviewers examined the subset of URLs identified as `valid_fsi` by the automated stage. Decisions focused on three questions: whether the organisation genuinely operated as a food sharing initiative, whether activity occurred within the target geography, and whether the source remained accessible and current.

Confirmed cases advanced to the validated dataset. Rejected entries were annotated with a structured category describing the reason for exclusion, together with a short explanatory note.

7.2 Incremental workflow

Verification proceeded cumulatively. Once a judgement had been recorded for a URL, it was retained across future rounds, and only newly discovered candidates required assessment. This approach substantially reduced repeated effort while preserving consistency in earlier decisions.

Over time, the dataset therefore evolved from exploratory discovery towards a progressively consolidated evidence base.

7.3 Manual verification and feedback

Manual review did not function solely as quality control. It also generated the feedback through which classification logic was clarified and improved.

To make this learning process systematic, rejected cases were recorded using a shared categorisation framework.

Table 3: False positive category

Category	Description
FP_MEDIA	News articles, media coverage
FP_COMMERCIAL	Commercial food services
FP_CROWDFUNDING	Crowdfunding campaigns
FP_MUSEUM	Museum exhibitions, cultural events
FP_GOVERNMENT	Government programme descriptions
FP_WRONG_LOCATION	Wrong city or country
FP_DUPLICATE	Duplicate of captured initiative
FP_NON_FSI_ORG	Food-related organisation, not an FSI
FP_SUPPORTING_ORG	Supports but does not operate FSI

Recording outcomes in this form enabled comparisons across cities and rounds. Recurrent categories revealed where automated interpretation diverged from domain expectations.

These observed regularities were translated into clearer instructions within subsequent prompts. For example, frequent FP_MEDIA outcomes led to explicit guidance distinguishing reporting *about* initiatives from pages representing the initiatives themselves.

Before deployment, proposed revisions were tested against the reference set to ensure that improvements in precision did not remove confirmed cases. Updated rules were then introduced in the following pipeline round, where new verification outcomes again became material for refinement.

Accuracy gains across versions therefore resulted from a cumulative process in which situated human judgements were progressively stabilised into reusable computational guidance.

7.4 Geographic confirmation

Location assignment served both representation and validation. Coordinates obtained through external services enabled initiatives to be placed on the map while also revealing instances in which an otherwise valid organisation operated outside the intended boundary. Such cases were reassessed during verification and frequently resulted in FP_WRONG_LOCATION annotations.

Together, these practices maintained traceability, transparency, and the capacity to revisit earlier decisions as definitions evolved.

8 Data organisation and persistence

Once discovery, classification, and verification had been completed, the pipeline required a structure capable of preserving earlier states of knowledge while enabling consistent transformation into research-ready outputs. The objective was not simply storage, but the stabilisation of decisions in a form that allowed comparison across rounds, traceability of revisions, and reuse in later analyses.

To achieve this, datasets were organised into three progressive levels corresponding to their epistemic status: *candidate*, *assessed*, and *validated*.

8.1 Candidate layer

The candidate layer preserves materials as they entered the pipeline. These include URLs discovered through search procedures, automation outputs, and externally compiled reference lists. Records at this stage retain ambiguity and may contain duplication, incomplete information, or incorrect geographic attribution.

Maintaining this layer ensures that earlier states remain recoverable, making it possible to audit how later decisions were reached or to re-run parts of the workflow under revised criteria.

8.2 Assessed layer

The assessed layer standardises and enriches candidate records so that they can be compared and linked. Transformations at this stage include format harmonisation, cleaning of textual fields, and the application of URL normalisation procedures that support entity resolution.

This layer functions as a bridge between uncertain discovery material and curated knowledge. It enables systematic matching between automated classification, ground truth references, and manual review outcomes, without yet asserting that any record represents a confirmed initiative.

8.3 Validated layer

The validated layer contains initiatives that have passed manual review and are considered suitable for analysis and public presentation. Records are consolidated, deduplicated, and augmented with additional attributes such as activity types, sharing modes, and geographic coordinates.

Because validated outputs underpin visualisation and reporting, transparency of provenance remains essential. Links to earlier pipeline stages are therefore preserved, allowing each confirmed initiative to be traced back to its discovery source and assessment history.

8.4 URL normalisation and entity resolution

A central requirement of consolidation was the ability to recognise when different web references corresponded to the same initiative. URL normalisation provided a lightweight mechanism for this purpose.

The process included protocol removal, case harmonisation, elimination of query strings and fragments, and consistent handling of trailing slashes. From these transformations, comparable identifiers were derived to support matching across automation outputs and manually curated lists.

Normalisation enabled both internal deduplication and the evaluation of recall against reference datasets. The full specification is provided in Appendix C.

8.5 Deduplication logic

Duplicate initiatives arise when the same organisation is represented by multiple web presences or when repeated discovery occurs across rounds. To address this, three complementary strategies were applied in sequence.

- Exact agreement of normalised keys (country, city, initiative name);
- Matching of normalised URLs within the same locality;
- High similarity in initiative names, flagged for additional review.

Together, these procedures removed 88 duplicate entries, reducing the dataset from 3,140 to 3,052 initiatives. Although numerically modest, these corrections materially affected city-level summaries and network interpretation.

8.6 Integrity checks

To ensure reliability across repeated executions, a suite of automated tests accompanied each run of the pipeline. These checks verified, for example, that identifiers remained unique, essential attributes were present, categorical values stayed within expected ranges, and counts remained internally consistent after transformation.

Rather than acting as a separate validation exercise, these controls were embedded within routine processing, ensuring that errors were detected immediately when introduced.

8.7 Relational structure

The overall model links discovery to curation through explicit relationships. Candidate URLs are associated with classification outcomes; assessed records connect these outcomes to review decisions; validated initiatives consolidate confirmed knowledge into stable entities.

This structure maintains a clear boundary between uncertainty and confirmation while preserving the possibility of revision. It allows the dataset to evolve without losing the history of how it was produced.

9 Outcomes

The implementation of the workflow resulted in a consolidated dataset of validated food sharing initiatives across the participating cities. This section summarises the scale of coverage achieved and the main effects of successive rounds of refinement. The purpose is not to offer a substantive interpretation of urban food systems, but to indicate what the methodology enabled in practice.

9.1 Scale of coverage

Across 105 cities, the pipeline produced 3,052 validated initiatives. The distribution is uneven. Some cities display dense ecosystems of organisations with strong online visibility, while others show sparse representation or rely on communication channels that are less easily captured through web discovery.

These differences reflect not only variation in activity but also structural asymmetries in language, digital presence, and institutional support. The pipeline therefore reveals both the geography of food sharing and the geography of visibility.

9.2 Improvement across versions

Performance increased substantially over successive rounds. The most significant gains occurred after the introduction of systematic exclusion logic and the stabilisation of prompt instructions derived from verification feedback. Later architectural changes further improved consistency and reduced operational overhead.

What is important is that improvement did not result from a single technical intervention. It emerged cumulatively through repeated interaction between automated judgement and situated human evaluation.

9.3 Effect of consolidation

Entity resolution and deduplication had a modest numerical impact but a disproportionate analytical one. Removing repeated representations of the same initiative altered city totals, network density, and activity distributions, thereby improving the reliability of comparative work.

The final dataset provides a stable foundation for mapping, visualisation, and cross-city examination, while retaining links to earlier stages that make future reassessment possible.

9.4 Availability of extended analysis

A more detailed statistical examination of geographic variation, activity profiles, language effects, and classification behaviour is presented in a separate project report. That document provides the full quantitative breakdown and city-level comparisons derived from the validated dataset.

10 Discussion

10.1 Methodological contributions

This study shows that large-scale identification of community-based initiatives from the open web can be organised in a systematic and repeatable manner while still retaining room for human judgement. Several methodological contributions stand out.

Iterative refinement as an organising principle. Accuracy gains did not result from a single technical change. Instead, they emerged from repeated cycles in which verification outcomes informed revisions to prompts, exclusion criteria, and decision procedures. The increase from 32% to 74% therefore reflects cumulative learning distributed across multiple rounds.

Retrieval-integrated classification. Bringing content retrieval and interpretation together simplified the overall workflow and reduced the practical effort required to rerun analyses. More importantly, the arrangement allowed quicker movement between automated judgement and human review, strengthening the iterative character of the system.

URL normalisation as entity resolution. Treating web addresses as entities requiring harmonisation rather than simple cleaning enabled consistent matching across heterogeneous sources. This proved crucial for reliable deduplication and evaluation.

Staged data refinement. Separating candidate material, intermediate assessments, and confirmed initiatives made it possible to retain uncertainty without allowing it to contaminate curated outputs. At the same time, earlier stages remained available for re-examination as classification logic evolved.

10.2 Challenges of multilingual web discovery

Working across many linguistic and national contexts revealed persistent difficulties that cannot be solved by automation alone.

- **Uneven digital visibility:** In some places initiatives maintain extensive web presences; in others they rely primarily on social media or informal communication, limiting discoverability.
- **Variation in terminology:** Expressions that perform well in one language may translate poorly into another, especially where compound words or local idioms dominate.
- **Platform dependency:** A large share of activity occurs in environments that are only partially accessible to search indexing and automated retrieval.

These issues mean that absence from the dataset should not be read as absence of activity.

10.3 Human judgement in automated classification

Experience from the project indicates that language models are most effective when embedded within structured processes of review. Initial runs demonstrated that generic classification without contextual adjustment produced high levels of error. Improvement became possible only once outcomes from verification were stabilised into clearer instructions.

Several observations follow.

- **Error patterns are recurrent.** Media reporting, commercial services, and umbrella organisations appeared repeatedly, allowing them to be addressed through explicit exclusion logic.
- **Verification remains necessary.** Even at later stages, automated outputs required confirmation before inclusion in the final dataset.
- **Learning is procedural.** The mechanism of progress lay in the relationship between review and reformulation rather than in the model alone.

10.4 Limitations

A number of constraints shape how the results should be interpreted.

1. Accuracy levels still require routine verification in each round.
2. Performance is generally stronger for English-language material than for some other linguistic contexts.
3. Exact replication depends on access to similar model behaviour and web content, both of which change over time.
4. Evaluation relies on reference material that may itself be incomplete.
5. The dataset captures a moment in time; initiatives evolve, appear, and disappear.

10.5 Implications for future mapping work

Beyond food sharing, the approach suggests a practical way to organise web-based discovery under conditions of ambiguity. Key

transferable elements include multilingual querying, explicit separation between candidate and validated knowledge, and the formal use of verification results to guide subsequent rounds.

Detailed empirical analyses derived from the dataset are presented in a separate summary report, which provides further statistical breakdowns and city-level comparisons.

11 Conclusion

This paper has described a structured method for identifying and curating urban food sharing initiatives across 105 cities. The approach combined multilingual search, model-assisted interpretation, and systematic verification within a process designed for repetition and revision.

The principal achievement is not full automation but the establishment of a stable relationship between computational assistance and situated human evaluation. Through successive rounds of refinement, accuracy improved substantially while transparency and traceability were maintained.

The resulting dataset now underpins a public map and provides a shared empirical foundation for further investigation of urban food sharing. More detailed analytical findings are reported separately in the project summary documentation.

Future development will focus on strengthening multilingual sensitivity, examining alternative classification strategies, and extending coverage to additional locations. Continued progress will depend less on model novelty than on maintaining the feedback structures that allow judgement to be revised in light of experience.

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A City coverage

The study covers 105 cities. They are listed below in alphabetical order by country and, within each country, by city.

Albania: Tirana **Armenia:** Yerevan **Austria:** Graz; Innsbruck; Linz **Belgium:** Antwerp; Ghent; Liège **Bosnia and Herzegovina:** Sarajevo **Bulgaria:** Plovdiv; Sofia; Varna **Croatia:** Rijeka; Split; Zagreb **Cyprus:** Famagusta; Limassol; Nicosia **Czech Republic:** Brno; Ostrava; Plzeň **Denmark:** Aalborg; Aarhus; Kolding **Estonia:** Narva; Tallinn; Tartu **Faroe Islands:** Tórshavn **Finland:** Helsinki; Oulu; Tampere **France:** Bordeaux; Lyon; Marseille; Nantes **Georgia:** Tbilisi **Germany:** Bremerhaven; Dresden; Freiberg **Greece:** Athens; Heraklion; Larissa; Patras **Hungary:** Budapest; Debrecen; Pécs **Iceland:** Reykjavík **Israel:** Jerusalem **Italy:** Bari; Milan; Palermo; Turin **Kosovo:** Pristina **Latvia:** Daugavpils; Liepāja; Riga **Lithuania:** Kaunas; Klaipėda; Vilnius **Luxembourg:** Dudelange; Esch-sur-Alzette; Luxembourg City **Malta:** Valletta; Victoria (Gozo) **Moldova:** Chişinău **Montenegro:** Podgorica **Morocco:** Rabat **Netherlands:** Ede; The Hague; Utrecht **New Zealand:** Auckland **North Macedonia:** Skopje **Norway:** Oslo **Poland:** Gdańsk;

Lublin; Wrocław **Portugal:** Braga; Lisbon; Torres Vedras **Republic of Ireland:** Cork; Dublin; Galway; Limerick **Romania:** Braşov; Cluj-Napoca; Constanţa **Serbia:** Belgrade **Slovakia:** Bratislava; Košice; Žilina **Slovenia:** Koper; Ljubljana; Maribor **Spain:** Barcelona; Palma de Mallorca; San Sebastián; Seville **Sweden:** Linköping; Malmö; Umeå **Tunisia:** Tunis **Turkey:** Ankara **Ukraine:** Kyiv **United Kingdom:** Brighton and Hove

B Evaluation of search configuration for geographic precision

Because many city names correspond to locations in more than one country, additional work was required to understand how search parameters influenced the geographic relevance of retrieved URLs.

A series of Google Custom Search configurations were therefore tested. These included a baseline setup, individual country or region restrictions, and a combined configuration that applied country parameters together with a national search domain (for example, `google.ie`). For each setup, returned URLs were examined using an LLM-based assessment of likely location. As a simple and conservative indicator of cross-border noise, we also counted links that clearly referred to places in the United States.

The differences between configurations were pronounced. Under the baseline setting, roughly 38% of URLs pointed to US-based content, while only about 17% could be confidently associated with the intended city. Introducing a country restriction (cr) markedly improved precision, increasing the share of city-consistent results to approximately 54%.

The most restrictive combination (country parameter, geolocation parameter, and national search domain) reduced clearly US-based results to almost zero (around 0.1%) while maintaining a similar proportion of city-relevant entries.

However, stronger filtering also created losses. Some international organisations and initiatives hosted on global platforms disappeared from the results, illustrating that tighter geographic control can reduce recall even as it improves precision.

For this reason, geographic identification during the discovery stage was treated as provisional. Final confirmation of location remained part of the manual verification process described in the main text.

C URL normalisation rules

To enable consistent matching across discovery outputs, manual verification records, and reference datasets, URLs were transformed into a standardised canonical form. The procedure removes elements that do not affect organisational identity (such as protocols, tracking parameters, or anchors) while preserving components necessary for domain-level comparison.

The pseudocode below summarises the transformations applied during the staging phase.

```
function normalise_url(url):
    url = remove_regex(url, '#.*$') // remove
    ↪ anchors
    url = remove_regex(url, '\?.*$') // remove
    ↪ query parameters
    url = remove_regex(url, 'https?://') // remove
    ↪ protocol
```

```
url = remove_regex(url, '^www\.') // remove
↳ www prefix
url = strip_trailing_slash(url)
url = lowercase(url)
url = unicode_nfk_normalise(url)
return url
```

```
function clean_text(text):
  text = unicode_nfk_normalise(text)
  text = lowercase(text)
  text = normalize_whitespace(text) // collapse
↳ repeated spaces
  text = standardize_apostrophes(text) // harmonise
↳ apostrophe forms
  text = remove_non_word_chars(text) // keep
↳ words and separators
  text = strip(text)
  return text
```

These steps supported reliable deduplication and stable comparison between automated outputs and manually curated records.

D Automation tool evolution and iterative refinement (v1.1.0–v1.9.0)

This appendix documents how the automation procedures developed across successive versions prior to the transition to the agent-based model. The account synthesises internal project records into methodological themes, focusing on adjustments that affected classification behaviour, multilingual reach, and data reliability.

Rather than presenting a full change log, the emphasis here is on how operational experience, especially insights gained through manual verification, was translated into more stable and reproducible computational guidance.

D.1 Prompt refinement and exclusion logic

Between v1.1.0 and v1.9.0, the classification prompts evolved through a series of incremental modifications aimed at reducing recurrent false positives.

Early iterations concentrated on distinguishing initiatives from media coverage. Subsequent adjustments broadened the scope of exclusion to include cultural venues, educational institutions, and umbrella organisations that appeared frequently in search results but did not directly operate food sharing activities.

Later versions introduced greater nuance. Certain institutional or municipal websites were allowed where operational responsibility for an initiative could be established. These exceptions reflected learning derived from repeated review of borderline cases.

Importantly, these developments occurred gradually, allowing individual changes to be observed and evaluated across rounds.

D.2 Knowledge-based filtering and blacklist development

Filtering mechanisms were progressively systematised as new noise patterns became visible.

Initial blacklists targeted widely recurring national and international media portals. From mid-series versions onwards, the process

became more automated. Public knowledge sources, particularly Wikipedia, were used to compile structured lists of newspapers, broadcasters, and similar domains, which were then incorporated into filtering routines. As the geographic scope expanded, additional region-specific sources were integrated.

This shift reduced reliance on manual domain entry while maintaining adaptability.

D.3 Expansion of multilingual coverage

Language support increased stepwise rather than all at once. New query sets were introduced as they became available and were validated through use. In multilingual countries, outputs from different language runs were subsequently reconciled through post-processing to avoid fragmenting representation across linguistic variants.

The gradual nature of expansion meant that search effectiveness improved unevenly, reflecting both linguistic complexity and varying degrees of local web visibility.

D.4 Geographic checks and duplicate handling

Geographic plausibility controls were introduced once large-scale cross-border confusion became evident in the retrieved data. From v1.2.0 onwards, candidate initiatives were geo-located using Google Places and the Google Geocoding API, and the resulting coordinates were then cross-verified against an independent source, Wikipedia, where available. Cases with inconsistent or conflicting location evidence were flagged for manual review, helping to reduce geographically noisy entities in the dataset.

Duplicate detection was also strengthened during this stage. In addition to URL-based checks, post-processing incorporated matching based on initiative names and domains, which reduced repeated representation of the same organisation, particularly in cities with dense and heterogeneous online ecosystems.

D.5 Entity naming conventions

Approaches to naming were tested and revised. An intermediate phase introduced parallel local-language and machine-translated English names to improve comparability. However, this strategy sometimes generated new ambiguities. Later versions therefore prioritised local-language naming in final outputs, favouring consistency over translation completeness.

D.6 Operational robustness

Alongside conceptual refinements, practical adjustments improved the stability of large-scale runs. These included parallelisation of tasks, improved handling of inaccessible URLs, and corrections to parsing and temporary storage routines. While less visible analytically, these changes were essential for maintaining continuity across repeated executions.

D.7 Methodological significance

Viewed together, the version history shows that accuracy gains emerged from accumulated operational learning rather than from model capability alone. Each cycle of verification exposed new regularities, which were then formalised into clearer prompts, filtering logic, or handling rules. Over time, this process aligned automated

interpretation more closely with domain expectations while preserving the ability to revise earlier assumptions.

E Second-stage filtering and prompt specification (v2.0.0)

To improve precision beyond the initial automation output, an additional classification pass was introduced. This second-stage filter operated on URLs already labelled as potential FSIs and aimed to address recurrent forms of misclassification, particularly those associated with media reporting, institutional descriptions, and indirect references.

Importantly, the baseline classifier remained unchanged at this point. The intervention therefore allows the effect of additional decision logic to be observed independently from changes in the original system.

E.1 Baseline system prompt

The initial system prompt used throughout early runs is reproduced below.

You are tasked **with** classifying webpages **as** valid **or**
 ↪ invalid food sharing initiatives (FSI) based on
 ↪ the URL **and** web text content. A valid FSI should
 ↪ engage **in or** support a limited **set** of activities:
 ↪ food sharing, food charity, food exchange, food
 ↪ cooperatives, sharing of cooking skills **or**
 ↪ knowledge, recipe sharing, sharing of cooking
 ↪ spaces, gardening skill **or** knowledge sharing,
 ↪ Community Supported Agriculture, **or** seed sharing.

Reject a webpage **as** an invalid FSI **if** it meets **any** of
 ↪ the following criteria:

- (1) the website primarily serves commercial purposes,
- (2) the activities are **not** located **in** the target city,
 ↪ **or**
- (3) the website solely features news articles about
 ↪ food sharing activities without directly
 ↪ participating **in** them.

E.2 Second-stage filtering prompt

The additional prompt applied stricter exclusion criteria to material that had already passed the baseline assessment. Its function was to stabilise borderline distinctions that repeatedly emerged during manual verification.

You are a second-stage filter for food sharing
 ↪ initiative (FSI) classification. Review the
 ↪ following URL and extracted text, which has
 ↪ already been classified as a potential FSI.

REJECT the URL if ANY of the following apply:

1. The page is primarily a news article, press
 ↪ release, or media coverage about food sharing
 ↪ (not the initiative itself).
2. The page describes a government programme or policy
 ↪ without evidence of an operational initiative.

3. The page is a crowdfunding campaign, grant
 ↪ application, or funding portal.
4. The page represents a museum exhibition, cultural
 ↪ event, or educational resource about food.
5. The organisation supports or funds FSIs but does
 ↪ not directly operate one.
6. The initiative is located outside the target city
 ↪ or country.
7. The page is a directory listing or aggregator, not
 ↪ the initiative's own website.

ACCEPT the URL only if it directly represents an
 ↪ operational food sharing initiative in the target
 ↪ city.

Output: "ACCEPT" or "REJECT" with a one-sentence
 ↪ reason.

E.3 Effect on classification outcomes

The second-stage filter was tested against the fixed reference set of 228 URLs, including 73 confirmed FSIs.

Stage	Candidates	Valid FSIs	Accuracy
Baseline	228	73	32.02%
After second-stage filter	106	73	68.87%

The intervention reduced the candidate set by more than half while retaining all confirmed initiatives. Most removals corresponded to recurring categories already visible in manual review, particularly media reporting, governmental descriptions, and supporting or umbrella organisations.

Following evaluation, this procedure became part of the standard workflow in version v2.0.0.

F Agent-based classification (v3.0.0)

This appendix documents the transition from the earlier crawl-based approach to an agent-mediated form of assessment. The aim was not only to improve accuracy but to constrain how evidence could be used in making decisions.

The experiment employed a fixed labelled reference set and a standardised output format, allowing performance to be compared with previous versions.

F.1 Input data

The evaluation used a JSON list of candidate URLs annotated with city and country metadata. The reference material consisted of:

- 228 candidate URLs produced by earlier runs;
- 73 initiatives confirmed through manual verification.

Source files are maintained within the project's internal repository.

F.2 Method

For each candidate, the model was asked to determine whether the website directly represented an operational initiative in the

specified location. The agent was permitted to consult the target site using a search tool and could rely only on information found there.

This adjustment narrowed the interpretive field. Rather than inferring validity from indirect references, listings, or contextual signals, the model had to ground its decision in explicit organisational evidence.

F.2.1 Instruction prompt.

Classify whether the given URL represents a valid Food Sharing Initiative (FSI) located in $\{city\}$, $\{country\}$.

Method:

Use `web_search` to review the website's main page and

- ↪ any linked "About," "Mission," or "Info" sections.
- ↪ Base your decision only on direct evidence found on the site.

VALID FSI \hat{A} all MUST be true:

1. Direct representation: The website is owned by or
 - ↪ officially represents the initiative (not a media article, listing, or directory).
2. Core activity = food sharing: The main and
 - ↪ explicitly stated purpose involves the redistribution or communal sharing of food \hat{A} e.g. community kitchens, free meals, food rescue, food cooperatives, seed/produce exchange, or shared gardens where harvest is collectively distributed.
 - Mentions of "sustainability," "community," or "ecology" without explicit food redistribution are insufficient.
3. Active food-sharing focus.
4. Ongoing operation.
5. Location match: The initiative operates in $\{city\}$, $\{country\}$.
6. Non-commercial.

INVALID FSI --- if any apply:

- News, media, or directory sites.
- Government listings without operational responsibility.
- Crowdfunding pages.
- Institutions hosting occasional events.
- Commercial services.
- Social media without verifiable ownership.
- Outside the specified location.
- Insufficient evidence.
- Inaccessible content.

Output (JSON only):

```
{
  "valid": true or false,
  "confidence": number between 0 and 1,
  "reason": string under 300 characters
}
```

City and country placeholders were substituted for each individual evaluation.

F.2.2 User prompt.

Classify this url: $\{url\}$

F.3 Models evaluated

Two models were tested under identical conditions.

Model	Accuracy	Estimated cost (USD)
gpt-5-mini	74.5%	0.82
gpt-5-nano	69.29%	0.37

F.4 Outputs

Model responses were preserved as raw logs for auditability and later inspection.

- 1762851298261--gpt-5-mini--classification-experiment-results.txt
- 1762851828097--gpt-5-nano--classification-experiment-results.txt